

LINGUOMADANIC CHARACTERISTICS OF STATE QUALITIES ASSOCIATED WITH A PHYSICAL DEFECT

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Annotation. While the status adjectives representing defective characters are minority, the semas "nomos to taste, unpleasant" combine. Therefore, it was shown that this subgroup is an archiseme of adjectives with the expression "inappropriate, unpleasant to taste". These adjectives were generally seen as adjectives denoting "ugliness". It was considered desirable to study the composition of sememas of each and, on this basis, to illustrate the sememas of each in order to realise the sememas of those qualities that express this ugliness through examples.

Key words. Adjectives denoting archisema, sema, semema, adjective, case adjective, ugliness.

The adjectives, generalizing with the archiseme "nomos to taste, unpleasant", expressing ugliness, are again divided into three groups, generalizing with their semas, such as "appearance", "organs and organs", "external state". Each of these semas has the task of generalizing some group of adjectives expressing ugliness, and serves as an integral sema for adjectival sememas in that group. Even more specifically, the adjective denoting ugliness, which is generalized by the archiseme "nomos to taste, unpleasant", consists of one semantic field, which is divided into a small field according to each integral semas. The semema of adjectives denoting ugliness in small spaces summarizes in this integral sema. This is characterized by each differential Sema of the adjectives in the subgroup. That is, the integral sema in the semem of adjectives is the sema, each of which indicates its own character.

The qualities of the archisema, which indicate ugliness, "inappropriate, unpleasant to taste", are ugly, badbashara, yapasqi, Brushy, slushy, olacooz, disabled, bald, blind, ramaqijan, desolate, lame, true, lame, bald, callador, callahum, bull, shirzada, chala, pale, pale, Leech, nimjon, crippled, vulgar, rough, besokay, beokshov, tannoz, consists of satang, olifta, disgusting, ipirisqi. The adjectives denoting this ugliness are divided into semantic fields according to three integral semas. This was also stated above. The integral semas of the first semantic field were given as "view". This view is taken from the point of view of a person. The appearance of a person is measured by the structure of the front side of his head. So, this includes the face, eyes, ears, nose, forehead and its upper parts, bow. These sememali adjectives, which generalize with integral

sema, are mainly composed of ugly, badbashara, yapasqi, brush, slime, olako'z, disabled, bald, blind, genuine. This qualitative semema is unique according to the two differential semas. This includes ugly, badbashara, yapasqi qualities, while the first is distinguished by the differential semas " facial structure". They are also differentiated by the pragmatic aspect of differential semas, though, the same as the denotative aspect. Sememas of ugly quality are unique in that they are inherent in oral speech, sememas of badbashara quality are inherent in general originality and strength of negative ottenka, sememas of yapasqi quality have a "structure" in mind and represent enlightenment. It is for this that these adjectives are realizable with illustrative examples. Since they are made realistic on the basis of illustrative examples, the character of these differential semas must be taken into account. Since differential semas are " facial structures", there will be an imbalance in facial structures, non-conformity. It sounds unpleasant with that. In a realistic illustrative example, the word ugly, badbashara, yapasqi should be replaced, as well as words or compounds that reveal these signs, non-conformity on the face. For example: *The Postman was more than fifty years old, a novice, a sick person, pale, with fallen teeth, a pale beard, a curly face, an ugly person.* The diseased, pale words and teeth in this sentence fell, the beard was pale, the facial curly compounds played a role in the realization of the meaning of the ugly word. As we know, the face of a sick person will be pale, pale is the numbness of the facial tone. Also, the fact that the teeth fell out, the beard turned white, the frizz of the face spoils the ugly appearance of the face. This is how the ugly word for a negative state of appearance served as a generalizing slice in the composition of the sentence.

In illustrative examples, a word whose semantics are attached to a word that needs to be realizable will also be important. A large role in this is played by the pragmatic correspondence of compound words, as well as the proportionality of semas in their sememas. For example: *it is necessary that I show The Ugly barzangi of this Turkey who I am, what I am capable of.* In this sentence, first of all, the combination of the word ugly with the word turq gave rise to the expression of negativity in the disparity of pragmatics in their semantics. The fact that Yana khunuk was the clarifier of barzangi was also of great importance in the realism of sememasi. Because the Uzbeks understand that barzangi is a non-existent Kaddi-a slender man . Such a person will be devoid of beauty.

While the ugly lexeme belongs to the semantic field of adjectives with an " inappropriate, unpleasant " archicemal sememe, it also has the integral SEMA

mentioned above. In this, the semema of the ugly lexeme expresses a sign of a certain object or reality, or psychic state. This semema of quality can be made real by the adjectival means to which it is attached. While an illustrative example is chosen for it, this linguistic tool should be kept in mind: for example: *...Looking at ugly depths like a willow in the middle of the Moss-blue grass, he was fantasizing. The old man rubbed each other so as not to go to other ugly fantasies. An ugly message came at a time when the arrival of Justice came near.* In the first of these statements, the depths, in the second, the fantasies, in the third, the words of the message played an important role for the opening of the meaning of the ugly word, showing what this meaning belongs to.

Badbashara quality is a character that is mainly aimed at a person, and it differs from the ugly word in the strength of the negativity paint. It is also possible to use the path applied to the realization of the sememas of ugly quality to make his sememas realistic. For example: *badbashara, who at one time turned thirty-five years old... the young man, sersokol, stood up and said a publisher who would print absurd stories for family readings in his newspaper...* To reveal the meaning of the badbashara quality in the sentence, the consonant combination as a young man was instrumental. The beard does not give a person beauty of growths and serfdom. It serves to decipher the meaning of the word badbashara. It is also possible to use antithesis when opening sememas of Badbashara quality: *Fazliddin, of course, is not badbashara, a tuppa-blunt guy from the look.* The statement uses tuppa-tuzuk antithesis from appearance to badbashara, which clarifies the semantics of badbashara quality.

In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word badchehra is explained in an example from the Uzbek language . This quality can be cited as synonymous with badbashara quality. But this adjective cannot be in Uzbek. It does not appear anywhere except in Oybeck's "looking for light". Because making a word from the word chehra with bad affixoid does not correspond to the Uzbek language's standard of making a word. Although the bad affixoid belongs to Iranian languages, the quality of badchehra has not borrowed from them. Because the cheek component has a positive pragmatic sema. The bad component, borrowed from Iranian languages, has a negative pragmatic sema in Uzbek. Components with negative and positive pragmatic sema cannot be combined and make words in Uzbek. Accordingly, it can be said that such a word in Uzbek is not made..

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